

Proclus Crater: mapping the spectral variability within Lunar Highlands

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Mafic regions embedded in the Lunar highlands have been recently observed [1] and, moreover, the presence of an absorption band at ca. 1250nm, assigned to Fe²⁺ transition in PL, has been detected in central peaks of some impact craters (e.g. [2]). Here, we analyze M3 (Chandrayaan mission) reflectance spectra of Proclus crater, a 28 km crater located in a highland portion on the west of Mare Crisium, where high amount of PL have been previously detected (e.g. [3]). First, we classified the crater in different spectral regions, using the Spectral Angle Mapper method, with a spectral library build by means of Purity Pixel Index, on the basis of the different spectral properties in the reflectance data. Then, we related the spectral parameters of each region to the mineralogical composition. To this purpose, the M3 data have been compared with laboratory spectra acquired on well characterized mixtures of PL and mafic minerals, such as pyroxene (PX) and olivine (OL) (e.g. [4] and references therein). We recognized regions with different spectral behaviors: 1) PL regions located mainly in the crater walls; 2) PX regions in both the walls and the floor of the crater; 3) OL regions in the south-east portion of the crater walls; and 4) PL (~90%)+PX regions in the crater wall. Here we have highlighted how a comparison with laboratory spectra can strongly help to obtain information about the mineral content and composition of a planetary surface. Moreover, a comparison with morphology and a 3D reconstruction is ongoing to assess a geological setting to this fresh crater and identify the origin of these mafic outcrops.

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References:

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